

IoT BASED MONITORING SYSTEM FOR WAREHOUSE SECURITY

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Abstract. Warehouse security management includes to make sure safety, to protect the quality of goods and to enhance the overall security of warehouses. The prioritize of “IoT Based Monitoring System for Warehouse” is to provide an effective and efficient solution for warehouses security against various threats such as fire, gas leakage, theft and unauthorized access. This system also focuses on offering real-time monitoring, detection and automatic responses with the combination of advanced sensors and modern technologies. The purposes of this system fully focus on various kinds of security solutions due to warehouses face with high accident rates. Implementing this IoT-Based system which is included modern IoT things and technologies can make timely detection, response, monitoring, immediate notifications and automatic responses. Therefore, this is crucial to prevent potential losses and to ensure the safety of warehouses.

Keyword: warehouses, security, enhance, solution, automatic, advanced, modern

INTRODUCTION

Most warehouses prioritize on how much goods can store, to store various kinds of goods with less worker. However, they forget to make sure the securities of warehouses and the importance of securities. Therefore, warehouses are not ready for the risks that are associated with unprotected risks such as theft, fire and unauthorized access. This lack of awareness can cause significant losses and disruption of progress. For example, the security system without combination of modern technologies and sensors may struggle to respond quickly various kinds of threats. “IoT-Based Monitoring System for Warehouse Security” is a crucial role in ensuring the safety and integrity of warehouses. The primary objective of this system is to offer modern technologies with advanced sensors to warehouses reducing risks and offering valuable solutions.

PROBLEM

This system is highly precious from the head, warehouse owners, to the tail, security. Ensuring the security and maintaining the quality of goods stored in warehouses is the most crucial part among operations. The secure inside and outside warehouse environment is essential for prevent the potential threat and can stable the business continuity. Therefore,

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

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monitoring and to handle threats should be prioritized. This IoT-based system provides an efficient and reliable solution for real-time monitoring and alerts. Because of this system, warehouses security become strong than before. Not only this but the usage of modern technologies brings the best solution for the needs of warehouses.

APPROACH

This system consists of two parts. There are Arduino Uno part and NodeMCU part. In Arduino part, the system setups MQ2 gas sensor and flame sensor. If the flame sensor is not detected the flame and the amount of gas is below 300, the system is safe. The buzzer and water pump are OFF but green led is ON. Otherwise, the flame sensor detects flame and gas value is below 300, the system is in a dangerous state. In this state the buzzer, water pump and red led is ON simultaneously. The Serial Monitor displays “Fire Alert! Take Action”. At the same time message sending “Fire Alert!!Take action Immediately” and calling process will be carried out through the GSM module. If the flame is not detected and the gas value is over 300, the system is indicating on imminent danger. Continuously, the buzzer and water pump are OFF and Orange LED is ON, gas value is displayed in the serial monitor. And then SIM900a GSM module sends a message “Gas leaked!!! Take action immediately” and calls the phone via GSM module. The Serial Monitor displays “Gas Leaked!!! No fire detected!!!”.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

In NodeMCU, the system setup MQ2 gas sensor and DHT11 sensor. Gas values, temperature value and humidity value are displayed on the LCD, Blynk console and Blynk mobile application. The Gas sensor sense the gas amount, and the gas value is over 300, Blynk notification will send “Unusual Gas Amount is detected !!!!!”. If it is under 300, “Fresh Air” will be shown on LCD. Figure 1 illustrates both Arduino Uno and NodeMCU parts.

Figure 2: System Block Diagram

Figure 2 illustrates system block diagram for both System. First is about Arduino Block Diagram. This system is centered around an Arduino Uno microcontroller, which is powered by a 12V power supply. The system uses two key sensors, a flame sensor and an MQ2 gas sensor, to detect the fire and gas leaks. The outputs of the Arduino are connected to several components: a 5V relay which controls a water pump to spray the fire, a buzzer for audible alert, an LED for visual alert, and a GSM module. GSM module enables to send notifications via SMS or calls. This setup ensures real-time responses and reduces potential security threats in the warehouse. NodeMCU Block Diagram is an IoT-based monitoring system using the ESP8266 Wi-Fi module. The system receives power from a 5V power supply and collects environmental data through two sensors: the DHT11 sensor and MQ2 gas sensor. These sensors are connected to the ESP8266 module. Then, it displays the relevant information on an LCD. For remote monitoring and notifications, the system uses Blynk platform, enabling live data to a smartphone and Blynk console website.

RESULTS

The design of “IoT-Based Monitoring System for Warehouse Security” is user-friendly and efficient. With this system, warehouse securities and awareness can easily assess with real-time monitoring data, view the dashboard on mobile for alerts, and the receive notifications with email and via SMS. Moreover, automatic system and continuous detection system can reduce human resources. Moreover, this system plan to enhance the system in the future to ensure reliable functionality even in areas with limited internet connectivity. This system serves

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

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as a direct link for users to monitor and manage warehouse security remotely, helping them to obtain accurate and timely information to protect their assets effectively.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

“IoT-Based Monitoring System for Warehouse Security” is made to enhance the security management of warehouses. This system is a important role in modern warehouses and ensuring the safety by providing real-time monitoring, automatic systems, visible and edible alerts. It helps preventing threats such as theft, fire, gas leakage and abnormal conditions. By integrating advanced IoT technologies, the system not only enhances the protection of valuable goods within the warehouses not only offers user-friendly features for everyone, specially security. In conclusion, improving warehouse security systems like this is vital for reducing risks, ensuring security and operation continuity and offering a more safe and efficient future for warehouses.

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